

**OPEN POLICY ROADMAP FOR
THE “OPEN EDUCATION for a BETTER WORLD (OE4BW)”
ONLINE MENTORING PROGRAM**

Student: Ana Fabjan
Mentors: prof. dr. Dominic Orr, prof. dr. Tel Amiel
Program: Master in Leadership in Open Education (LOE), University of Nova Gorica
Course: Open Education Strategies
Year: 2020/21

This work is licensed CC BY SA 4.0

CONTENT

1	INTRODUCTION	1
1.1	Basic information about the OE4BW program.....	1
1.2	Project context.....	2
1.2.1	OE4BW potential for achieving the Agenda 2030	2
1.2.2	Use of open licences and technical openness.....	3
2	IDENTIFYING A NEED FOR POLICY.....	3
2.1	Defining challenges or problems.....	4
2.2	The significance of OER	4
2.3	Formulating vision statement	4
3	FRAMING THE OER POLICY	5
3.1	Scale and scope.....	5
3.2	Stakeholders.....	6
4	GAP ANALYSIS	6
4.1	Framework.....	7
4.2	The Open Education Policy Game as diagnosis and discussion tool	7
5	MASTERPLAN.....	9
5.1	A summary view of the OER masterplan.....	9
6	GOVERNANCE AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN.....	11
6.1	The implementation plan	11
7	LAUNCH.....	12
8	REFERENCES	12

1 INTRODUCTION

The idea of this paper is to present a OER policy for the online mentoring program “Open Education for a Better World” (OE4BW)¹ through a policymaking process described in the “Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies” by Miao et al. (2019) and activity called the “Open Education Policy Game”². The proposed process has seven phases in which I first seek to identify the need for a OER policy, continue to map the vision, scale and scope, and stakeholders that the program engages, then propose a framework to assess the “open up” aspect of the program, and finally construct a summary view of the OER masterplan that provides an operational foundation for policy development. The Open Education Policy game aims to make a diagnosis of the potential for openness in the OER policy and complements the evaluation phase of the guidelines.

1.1 Basic information about the OE4BW program

On September 2017, the 2nd World Open Educational Resources (OER) Congress³ was held in Ljubljana, Slovenia, with the theme “OER for Inclusive and Equitable Quality Education: From Commitment to Action”, focusing on the role of OER in achieving Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4⁴. The event prompted the Commonwealth of Learning⁵ to issue a Global Report on Open Educational Resources (OER) which presented the current state of OER worldwide and identified concrete actions to include OER to achieve SDG4 (COL, 2017). The study concluded that the development of OER is very uneven across regions and, despite the promotion of cooperation, largely individual with little attention paid to practical implementation (Urbančič et al., 2019).

Source: Personal archive licensed CC BY SA 4.0

As a response to the lack of opportunities for obtaining knowledge and skills needed to design, implement, use and reuse OER the online mentoring program “Open Education for a Better World” was developed by the University of Nova Gorica⁶ in collaboration with the UNESCO Chair on Open Technologies for Open

¹ OE4BW (<https://oe4bw.org/>)

² Open Education Policy Game (<https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/>)

³ 2nd World OER Congress (<https://www.oercongress.org/>)

⁴ Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 4 (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals/goal4>)

⁵ Commonwealth of Learning (<https://www.col.org/>)

⁶ University of Nova Gorica (<http://www.ung.si/en/>)

Educational Resources and Open Learning⁷ at Jožef Stefan Institute (Urbančič et al., 2019). OE4BW has the aim of bringing together real-life practice in education and expertise in the area of OER through a mentoring and support program.

1.2 Project context

Since its beginnings in October 2017, the OE4BW mentoring program has gained a steadily growing network of OER practitioners and experts. The success of the OE4BW program has shown that there is enough motivation and need for progress in the field of Open Education to start a bottom-up movement linking Open Education and the UN Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)⁸ (Urbančič et al., 2019). The Open Education practices and OER developed and tested in the OE4BW program have the potential to be transferred beyond the scope of the OE4BW community. The program would benefit from an appropriate OER policy, that would encourage the use and reuse of the developed OER outside the program area and allow stakeholders to make informed decisions about promotion and collaboration.

OE4BW ADDRESSES TOPICS IN RELATION WITH THE SDGs

Source: Personal archive licensed CC BY SA 4.0

1.2.1 OE4BW potential for achieving the Agenda 2030

The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development⁹ is a plan of action adopted by all United Nations Member States in 2015. It resolves that, between now and 2030, all countries will take transformative steps to eradicate poverty in all its forms and dimensions. The scale and ambition of the Agenda is demonstrated with the 17 SDGs and their associated 169 targets. They recognize ending poverty must go hand-in-hand with strategies that build economic growth and address a range of social needs including education, health, equality and job opportunities, while tackling climate change and working to preserve our ocean and forests.

⁷ UNESCO Chair on Open Technologies for OER and Open Learning (<https://unesco.ijs.si/>)

⁸ UN 17 SDGs (<https://sdgs.un.org/goals>)

⁹ 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (<https://sdgs.un.org/2030agenda>)

UNESCO has been entrusted to lead the Global Education 2030 Agenda¹⁰ through SDG 4. Although access to education is a fundamental human right and plays a crucial role in the path towards all other SDGs, it is far from being guaranteed for all. One of the ways to address this major challenge is through the use of OER, which break down different types of barriers, from economic to cultural to social and political (Urbančič et al., 2019).

OE4BW promotes the creation and dissemination of OER in line with the SDGs, particularly focusing on SDG 4 - ensuring inclusive and equitable quality education and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all. The program is run on a voluntary basis, with stakeholders motivated by the importance of the SDGs. It is open to all, regardless of their professional background, education, citizenship or any other limiting factors. Accepted proposals are selected based on their compatibility with the SDGs, social impact, maturity of the idea, ability and commitment of the applicant to implement the idea. The program connects developers of OER with experts who are willing to engage as mentors in an informal online mentoring relationship that allows a high degree of flexibility in working together in different locations (Urbančič et al., 2019).

The program therefore addresses two major challenges:

- providing quality education that develops creativity and knowledge and ensures the acquisition of the basic literacy and numeracy skills, as well as high level analytical, problem-solving and other cognitive, interpersonal and social skills;
- promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all with access to non-formal learning. (Miao et al., 2019)

1.2.2 Use of open licences and technical openness

OE4BW supports the development and implementation of openly available modules and resources. The scope and final form of the OER developed are not prescribed, nor is the platform to be used. This is to encourage participants to find the best solution for their target audience and specific context. The only requirement is that the educational material developed is publicly available and identified as such through the use of an appropriate open licence¹¹. (Urbančič et al., 2019)

2 IDENTIFYING A NEED FOR POLICY

In the Global Report on Open Educational Resources (OER), the lack of appropriate policy solutions was identified as one of the biggest challenges to mainstreaming OER. The most frequently cited skills needed to improve OER use were information and communication technology (ICT) skills (i.e. a high level of digital literacy), followed by understanding open licences and how they work, assessing utility and determining the value and quality of OER, and sharing OER (COL, 2017).

The OE4BW program has recognized the need for obtaining knowledge and skills in OER development, built a community of stakeholders around it and developed a successful model which has enabled the community to thrive. In 2021, over 200 people are involved in the global network.

However, to enable OE4BW to progress from an emerging network, to a stable and growing community, there is a need to develop and implement a clearer strategy for the future. This means making decisions which will shape priority areas, scope and main focus objectives. The goal of this paper is to sketch out first considerations for a clear vision for OE4BW and its contribution to the implementation of OER across the globe (Miao et al., 2019, p. 20).

¹⁰ UNESCO - Leading SDG 4 (<https://en.unesco.org/themes/education2030-sdg4>)

¹¹ Creative Commons licences (<https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/>)

2.1 Defining challenges or problems

The following identify challenges, which OE4BW is trying to address:

- **Increasing collaboration opportunities between different stakeholders**
This is the central focus of OE4BW. Online mentoring is key to the program's success and can be understood as an equitable network building where different stakeholders find opportunity for sharing and cross-sector collaboration.
- **Improving the relevance of learning content to individual needs**
The program encourages developers from around the world to use open digital tools and technologies which, combined with a tailored mentoring approach and with the outputs available under an open license to everyone, increase stakeholder engagement, personalisation and active participation.
- **Reducing barriers to learning opportunities for underserved groups**
The program supports development and implementation of openly available modules and resources for online education on topics with social impact according to the UN Sustainable Development Goals.
- **Reducing the costs of access to education**
The program aims to develop sustainable model for development of OER and capacity building by employing mentoring to reflect and build practical knowledge. The online mentorship model has a high level of flexibility that enables connectivity and participation at a global scale.

2.2 The significance of OER

The program's efforts to develop a sustainable model of capacity building for use, reuse and sharing of OER through collaboration and strategic partnerships addresses a major concern for the OER community.

2.3 Formulating vision statement

The policy vision for OE4BW is to harness online mentoring relationships and active participation in the development of OER to address social impact issues in line with the UN SDGs.

Short-term expectations

The OE4BW program provides an open, collaborative online environment for discovery, use and reuse of the developed OER, which can be freely used under Creative Commons licences. It brings together various stakeholders to collaborate on the development and deployment of OER.

Long-term expectations

The OE4BW program addresses the issues of its sustainability and continuation, and provides appropriate mechanisms for evaluating OER. The program envisages further engagement at regional, national and thematic levels which would diversify the program and encourage greater collaboration.

3 FRAMING THE OER POLICY

To develop a cohesive and comprehensive policy, there must be discussion on several strategic considerations that will constitute the framework of the policy (Miao et al., 2019, p. 33).

3.1 Scale and scope

The OE4BW participant network has grown over the years, as is indicated in the table and graphs below, through combining a top-down approach with a focus on providing knowledge of best practices to the development and implementation of OER by developers already interested in this area (bottom-up). This approach to promoting informal and lifelong learning, which actively involves a group of committed individuals such as the hub coordinators, mentors and developers, has the potential to lead to adjustments in policy frameworks to enable greater discoverability and use of OER. The knowledge generated can be used to refine concepts, ICT strategy and regulatory factors to enable implementation and scaling of the OE4BW program.

TABLE: NUMBER OF OE4BW PARTICIPANTS OVER THE YEARS

YEAR	DEVELOPERS	MENTORS	HUB COORDINATORS
2017/18	14	27	/
2018/19	35	40	4
2019/20	80	66	9
2020/21	104	97	12

OE4BW GEOGRAPHIC DISTRIBUTION OVER THE YEARS

2017/18 - 14 developers / 27 mentors

2018/19 - 35 developers / 40 mentors / 4 hub coordinators

2019/20 - 80 developers / 66 mentors / 9 hub coordinators

2020/21 - 104 developers / 97 mentors / 12 hub coordinators

Source: Personal archive licensed CC BY SA 4.0

The program policy is aligned with the Ljubljana OER Action Plan from the Second World OER Congress which presents 41 recommended actions to mainstream open-licensed resources to help all Member States to build Knowledge Societies and achieve the 2030 Sustainable Development Goal 4 on “quality and lifelong education.” It provides recommendations to stakeholders in five strategic areas, namely: building the capacity of users to find, re-use, create and share OER; language and cultural issues; ensuring inclusive and equitable access to quality OER; developing sustainability models; and developing supportive policy environments.¹²

3.2 Stakeholders

The program brings together multiple stakeholders within the network:

- **Program coordinators**
Program coordinators have developed the methodology of the OE4BW program. They coordinate and monitor the overall progress of the program, and implement changes to improve collaboration and process to transform ideas into scalable and sustainable OER projects in line with the UNESCO Global Education 2030 Agenda.
- **Advisory board**
It is a board of experts in open education that provides the program coordinators actionable strategic advice and informed guidance for the development of the program. They have an important role in framing the program’s policy and can act as a catalyst for change.
- **Hub coordinators**
Experts with experience in development and deployment of OER are selected to serve as hub coordinators. They track progress during the project development phase and are responsible for organisational tasks, following the methodology developed by the program coordinators and working closely with them. They contribute to the promotion of the OE4BW programme in their regional and professional environment.
- **Mentors**
The mentors guide and advise the developers on the implementation of their OER in individually arranged online sessions. They come from all over the world with different professional backgrounds.
- **Developers**
Developers are people with diverse backgrounds and experiences that are selected based on their idea and motivation to develop and deliver OER (e.g. an open textbook), as well as on how their idea aligns with the SDGs. Developers are responsible for their project in terms of completion, delivery and dissemination.

4 GAP ANALYSIS

The purpose of the gap analysis is to understand the actual situation upon which the policy will be built, and to assess the areas and extent of the change to be made to reach the expected situation formulated in the policy vision (Miao at al., 2019, p. 45).

¹² Ljubljana OER Action Plan (<https://www.oercongress.org/woerc-actionplan/>)

4.1 Framework

- **Awareness and knowledge of key stakeholders about open licensing and OER**

The level of awareness among the stakeholders regarding the use of open licences and OER varies, where developers likely know less regarding the topics when starting the program. There are some measures in place to enable better understanding of the topics, e.g. every potential developer is required to complete a free online course on OER available on the COL website¹³.

- **Availability and accessibility of high-quality content**

The program has an official website that showcases all of the OER developed, but there has been a desire expressed by the developers for more interaction. Since 2020, efforts have been made to establish a collaborative, open online environment to facilitate the discovery, use and reuse of the OE4BW materials. More development and clearer guidelines are needed on that part. All materials are developed in the OE4BW program. It is a community-based model where OE4BW developers contribute to the creation of OER.

- **Regulation framework to support the creation and use of OER**

Currently, the program enables the use of OER, but the material is not easily discoverable. The need for such a framework has been recognized and initial steps have been taken to set up an evaluation of the OER material produced and to bring the OER material into an online environment so that it becomes discoverable and available for reuse.

- **ICT infrastructure and connected digital devices to support access to and management of OER**

ICT infrastructure and connected digital devices are a gap in policy and should be addressed, especially as developers come from regions where access to ICT and the internet is limited. The use of such devices would prove beneficial in improving accessibility.

- **Capacity of users to develop and use OER in the field**

At the core of the online mentoring program is to engage developers in the process to obtain, improve and retain the skills and knowledge needed to develop OER. Developers from diverse backgrounds are guided by volunteer mentors who have the skills needed to develop, implement, and deploy OER. It is a highly personalized process of learning-by-doing.

4.2 The Open Education Policy Game as diagnosis and discussion tool

The Open Education Policy Game was developed for educational management staff, responsible for the pedagogical, technical and legal-administrative sectors of public and private institutions. This game is designed to be played exclusively in teams. Its mechanics may suffer limitations if applied in other contexts, at the risk of being unsuitable for other audiences. To begin, one must define an educational policy to be analysed, and should invite a team composed of managers involved in three main areas: pedagogical, technical and legal-administrative.¹⁴

The purpose of the game was to identify and explore the potential for openness of the policy of OER, the development of the material, the quality assurance, the technical and legal requirements that enable the free and open distribution of the material and its reuse.

¹³ COL Understanding Open Educational Resources (<https://learnoer.col.org/login>)

¹⁴ Open Education Policy Game (<https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/>)

Within the course, the game was used as a diagnosis tool, especially for the gap analysis. The main findings are summarised in the following table "The Open Education Policy Game Results". The challenges for an open education policy are noted in the left-hand column and the responses from the three players, i.e. their own subjective judgements on the case in hand (OE4BW) are noted in the other columns.

The results of the game showed that the OE4BW program, with its growing number of participants and materials produced, would benefit greatly from a clear set of guidelines for open licensing, development of OER, quality and curation of OE4BW materials. The documents would help validate the work of OE4BW participants and facilitate greater use, reuse and remixing of OE4BW materials. Such engagement and clear guidelines would help build a more proactive community and promote the OE4BW program to a wider audience.

TABLE: THE OPEN EDUCATION POLICY GAME RESULTS

DIAGNOSIS OF THE OE4BW POLICY			
CHALLENGE	PLAYER 1	PLAYER 2	PLAYER 3
Is there a digital repository for OERs within the program?	No.	The coordinators of the SDG7 hub (which is a part of OE4BW) have created a digital library on the MiTeam platform.	There is a portfolio of OERs on the official OE4BW website. A repository is being developed at the MiTeam platform.
Can developers choose or switch between technologies?	We have to be mindful. Technological lock-in can be an issue for sustainable development of the program.	There are no preferences.	Developers are not obliged to use a certain technology to develop their OERs, however the OE4BW program uses a WordPress website to showcase the OERs and the MiTeam platform for online events.
Is the source code known?	We do not know.	We do not know.	We do not know.
Is the use of open licences specified?	No. Licensing needs to be specified in an official document.	There is a general agreement.	There is no document in which the use of open licences would be specified. We need it.
Is there a privacy policy in place?	There is no GDPR.	No.	There is none at the moment.
Does the program use free software?	The OE4BW participants are not aware of it. This needs to be addressed.	We need to start thinking about this.	This issue needs to be aligned with the program's vision.
Are there educational policies in place?	No. Needs to be developed and implemented.	For SDG7 there wasn't much limitation, but not necessarily for all others in the OE4BW community.	There is no such policy at the moment. It would be beneficial for the development and future planning.
Are the guidelines for OER developed within the program known?	No. It's very important to have guidelines, for better promotion and cooperation.	The guidelines would help (e.g. OE4BW logo is useful for promotion and reputation as it connected the OE4BW program to UNESCO Chair/UNG).	The guidelines are important to stimulate all stakeholders in better engagement and cooperation.
Is there a curatorship of the OERs within the program?	The MiTeam repository is being developed, but needs classification for better visibility and discoverability.	In the SDG7 hub the coordinators take care of the curatorship.	It is also important to note that this should be done collaboratively involving all OE4BW community and to put a rating system in place.

5 MASTERPLAN

The masterplan is the document consisting of specific building blocks for the whole policy. Together, these building block give the policy an operational foundation (Miao at al., 2019, p. 57).

5.1 A summary view of the OER masterplan

8 KEY BUILDING BLOCKS	OBJECTIVES	MAIN ACTIVITIES AND TARGET SECTORS	KEY PARTNERS FOR IMPLEMENTATION	INDICATORS
Adopting an open licensing framework	To enable and simplify the use of open licensing for OE4BW materials.	<p>Ensure that all OE4BW related materials are released under open licences.</p> <p>Encourage developers and mentors to use open licensing for self-generated content outside the scope of the OE4BW program.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators to ensure that open licensing is a condition of developed OER projects.</p> <p>Mentors of the OE4BW programme for implementing and verification.</p>	<p>Normative: Open licensing regulations of OE4BW materials.</p> <p>Quantitative: All OE4BW materials are openly licenced.</p>
Ensuring integration of OER at the level of curriculum development	To enable the use of OER developed in the OE4BW program.	Provide guidelines for the use of OE4BW materials.	OE4BW program coordinators who advocate skills development and provide lifelong learning opportunities for adults.	Normative: Guidelines for the use of OE4BW materials.
Ensuring the development, storage and accessibility of OER	To make OE4BW materials easily discoverable, accessible and adaptable through digital repository that allow storage and editing.	<p>Encourage OE4BW developers to use, reuse and remix OER.</p> <p>Develop the OE4BW repository to advocate for OER and encourage open format for storing digital data.</p> <p>Adopt metadata standards to facilitate discoverability of OE4BW materials.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators to set up incentives for engaged OE practitioners (e.g. certificates, exchange community...)</p> <p>IT experts for repositories and data links.</p> <p>Design experts for user-friendly interfaces.</p>	<p>Normative: There are clear metadata standards for the OE4BW platform.</p> <p>Quantitative: All or most OE4BW materials are aligned to defined metadata standards, which facilitate their discoverability.</p>
Aligning quality assurance procedures	To ensure appropriate quality assurance procedures, which encourage continual improvement and better use of OE4BW materials.	<p>Define and adopt regulations relating to assuring the quality of OE4BW materials.</p> <p>Allow for both, standard-based and community-assessed quality assurance procedures for OE4BW materials.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators together with advisory board set up a review process.</p> <p>Mentors assist in the review process.</p> <p>Peer-to-peer evaluation of OE4BW materials.</p>	<p>Normative: Quality assurance is adopted by the OE4BW program.</p> <p>The OE4BW repository allows community to rate OER.</p> <p>Number of certified OE4BW materials.</p>

<p>Supporting capacity building and awareness raising</p>	<p>To ensure that all stakeholders are aware about the qualities of OER and how they can be used.</p> <p>To enable OE4BW community access to quality OER for their use.</p>	<p>Launch campaigns on OE4BW program, showcasing developers and their production.</p> <p>Prepare and launch OE4BW short courses and webinars promoting OER and open licensing.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators, advisory board, hub coordinators, mentors and developers.</p>	<p>Normative: Courses and webinars are open to the OE4BW community.</p> <p>Quantitative: Share of participants who have successfully completed the courses each year.</p>
<p>Encouraging sustainable business models and launching funding strategies</p>	<p>To ensure that the cycle of OE4BW production and reuse is sustainable over time.</p>	<p>Develop OE4BW funding policy.</p> <p>Proactively seek funding opportunities and establish connection with other OER related programs, initiatives and projects.</p> <p>Ensure adequate incentives (time, money, participation in live events) for OE4BW developers and mentors.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators and advisory board.</p>	<p>Normative: Procedures exist to reward OE4BW developers and mentors.</p> <p>Quantitative: Share of partnering institutions.</p> <p>Amount of incentives for OE4BW developers and mentors.</p>
<p>Establishing monitoring and research on the effectiveness of OER use and learning outcomes</p>	<p>To ensure that continual monitoring of the OE4BW program’s progress.</p>	<p>Set up appropriate performance measurements to monitor the program’s capacity building (number of developers who have successfully completed the OE4BW courses, number of developers with developed certified OER, etc.).</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators, advisory board, hub coordinators and mentors.</p>	<p>Normative: A continual monitoring scheme exists.</p> <p>Quantitative: Number of developers who got OE4BW course certificate.</p> <p>Number of OE4BW developers who developed certified OER.</p>
<p>Setting up of a governing body to oversee and monitor the implementation of OER policy</p>	<p>To develop OE4BW standards and quality measures for OER.</p> <p>To monitor the progress of the OE4BW program and make course corrections.</p>	<p>Consultations with OE4BW advisory board to develop guidelines for monitoring OE4BW program development.</p> <p>OE4BW progress reporting and decisions on policy adjustment.</p>	<p>OE4BW program coordinators, advisory board, hub coordinators and mentors.</p>	<p>Normative: Frequency of meetings.</p> <p>Actions taken by the OE4BW program coordinators to achieve the objectives of the policy.</p>

6 GOVERNANCE AND IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

The governance and implementation plan is the high-level administrative and operative strategy behind the policy. It is about how the policy set out in the masterplan will be governed and executed to secure the engagement of key stakeholders and to set performance indicators for monitoring progress (Miao at al., 2019, p. 78).

6.1 The implementation plan

The premise of the implementation plan is that it must be prepared and executed collectively, as it affects stakeholders at all levels of the OE4BW program. Below is an outline I have prepared suggesting how such an implementation could be done. It combines methods of bottom-up activation, top-down steering and monitoring and wider outreach for more engagement in the wider community.

Establishing a balanced method of implementation

The strategy is primarily aimed at supporting developers and mentors of the OE4BW program. It uses the self-directed motivation of the OE4BW community to recognize and build upon the strategic framework. It is focused on the short term expectations where the OE4BW community drives the success of the program. However, this approach does not lead to a balanced implementation, so more top-down elements are needed.

Allocating resources and setting KPIs for implementation

There are two steps to centralising the monitoring of progress for the program; setting the milestones for the targets and setting the time and goal based KPIs. There are some explicit milestones for program activities and progress is monitored through KPIs. In future development, more information will be available and these two steps will form the basis of the annual monitoring plan.

Planning a partner engagement strategy

The strategy for wider consultation and increasing stakeholder engagement was to first set up advisory board which actively participates in the consultation process with the OE4BW program coordinators. The board helps to provide early insights into areas where the approach is too ambitious or needs more support, and ensure that stakeholders are properly empowered and informed about the overall masterplan.

Setting up an organizational structure for policy governance and coordination

Governance and coordination of the OE4BW program is centrally organized and closely linked to UNESCO via the UNESCO Chair of Open Technologies for Open Educational Resources and Open Learning.

The organizational structure consists of several interlinked parts:

- OE4BW Program Coordinators, together with the Advisory Board, form a central governing body that guides, supports and oversees the implementation of the program.
- Hub Coordinators are a coordinating body charged with leading the team and collaboration.
- Mentors are individuals charged with policy implementation.

Making use of international collaboration

As mentioned above, the OE4BW program is directly linked to UNESCO and should benefit from its community to plan and organise a participatory multi-stakeholder co-creation forum where stakeholders can meet, discuss and seek agreements for developing policies and procedures (Atenas et al., 2020). Such engagement can increase access, equity, quality, cost, inclusion, and innovation.

7 LAUNCH

After the planning is completed, the policy goes through an endorsement and launch process. The launch is not the end of the policy process, but only one phase in a longer-term implementation and learning process. A communication strategy needs to be designed to ensure that key stakeholders are sufficiently informed about the policy objectives and planned activities within the masterplan. The challenge is to put the plan into action. The use of various forms of media is recommended to inform these (and other) groups about the policy (Miao et al., 2019, pp. 90-91).

To inform and engage existing and prospective participants of the OE4BW program should create a short video summarizing the program's open policy and prepare accompanying text in multiple languages. In addition, OE4BW already organizes an annual event where the community gathers to share and discuss the progress of OER. This widely recognized and well-received event has great potential to bring together key stakeholders for the implementation of the policy.

However, in addition, webinars and networking events could be organized throughout the year (including showcasing the work of individual developers) for external decision makers to keep up the engagement in how OE4BW can really be achieving its vision of harnessing online mentoring relationships and promoting active participation in the development of OER to address social impact issues in line with the UN SDGs. The monitoring tools established for the policy implementation will be used to keep the strategic development of OE4BW open to improvement and even more ambitious growth and depth.

8 REFERENCES

Atenas, J. Havemann, L., Neumann, J. & Stefanelli, C. (2020). Open Education Policies: Guidelines for co-creation. Open Education Policy Lab, London. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4281363>. Last accessed 6th February 2021.

COL (2017). Open Educational Resources: Global Report 2017. Burnaby: COL. Available at: <http://oasis.col.org/handle/11599/2788>. Last accessed 6th February 2021.

Inamorato dos Santos, A. (2017) Going Open – Policy Recommendations on Open Education in Europe (OpenEdu Policies). Ed: Punie, Y., Scheller, K.D.A., EUR 28777 EN, Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg, 2017, ISBN 978-92-79-73496-0, doi:10.2760/111707, JRC107708. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/jrc/en/publication/eur-scientific-and-technical-researchreports/opening-education-support-framework-higher-education-institutions>. Last accessed 6th February 2021.

Miao, F., Mishra, S., Orr, D., Janssen, B. (2019), Guidelines on the development of open educational resources policies, UNESCO, Commonwealth of Learning, ISBN: 978-92-3-100341-7. Available at: <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000371129>. Last accessed 6th February 2021.

Open Education Policy Game. Available at: <https://aberta.org.br/oe-game/>. Last accessed 6th February 2021.

Urbančič, T., Polajnar, A., & Jermol, M. (2019). Open Education for a Better World: A Mentoring Programme Fostering Design and Reuse of Open Educational Resources for Sustainable Development Goals. *Open Praxis*, 11(4), 409–426. <https://openpraxis.org/index.php/OpenPraxis/article/view/1026/639>